

NEURON NETWORKS BASED ON ACOUSTIC MODELING OF SPEECH SIGNALS

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Annotation. Speech detection is a function of the technologies that enable voice access in a given system. Currently, along with traditional methods of inputting commands to technologies, such as pressing the buttons of a traditional device and sliding the screen, voice commands are also widely used. This approach provides convenience and efficiency for both hardware and software users. In this paper, effective methods for acoustic modeling of speech signals based on neural networks are investigated.

Key words : ANN model , automatic speech recognition system (ASR), neural networks (NN), Markov model, Dynamic Scaling (DMS), Speech to Text (STT)

НЕЙРОННЫЕ СЕТИ, ОСНОВАННЫЕ НА АКУСТИЧЕСКОМ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИИ РЕЧЕВЫХ СИГНАЛОВ

Аннотация. Обнаружение речи - это функция технологий, которые обеспечивают голосовой доступ в данной системе. В настоящее время, наряду с традиционными методами ввода команд в технологии, такими как нажатие кнопок традиционного устройства и перемещение экрана, также широко используются голосовые команды. Такой подход обеспечивает удобство и эффективность как для пользователей аппаратного, так и для программного обеспечения. В данной работе исследуются эффективные методы акустического моделирования речевых сигналов на основе нейронных сетей.

Ключевые слова : Модель AND, система автоматического распознавания речи (ASR), нейронные сети (NN), Марковская модель, динамическое масштабирование (MDS), преобразование речи в текст (STT),

NEYRON TARMOQLARIGA ASOSLANGAN NUTQ SIGNALLARINI AKUSTIK MODELLASHTIRISH

Annotatsiya. Nutqni aniqlash – ma’lum bir tizimda ovoz orqali kirishni ta’minlaydigan texnologiyalar funksiyasi hisoblanadi. Hozirgi paytda texnologiyalarga buyruq kiritishning an’anaviy qurilmaning tugmalarini bosish, ekranni surish kabi usullari qatorida ovoz orqali buyruqni amalga oshirish ham keng foydanilmoqda. Ushbu usul qurilmalar hamda dasturiy ta’minot foydalanuvchilari uchun qulaylik va samaradorlikni ta’minlamoqda. Ushbu maqolada neyron tarmoqlariga asoslangan nutq signallarini akustik modellashtirishning samarali usullari tadqiq qilingan.

Kalit so’zlar: ANN modeli, nutqni avtomatik aniqlash tizimi (ASR), neyron tarmoqlari (NN), Markov modeli, Dinamik masshtablash (DMS), Speech to Text (STT)

Introduction. Another type of models used in acoustic-phonetic modeling of speech are ANN models, the file signal and principles of which are biological models of the human nervous system. Information is transmitted to the neuron through discrete-time input connections, on the basis of which an output signal is formed, which is transmitted to the inputs of self-controlling neurons. In addition to improving the recognition of speech signals, ANNs are also used for acoustic modeling. Depending on the method of combining HMM and ANN in modeling, they are divided into hybrid and tandem neural network models. ANN can be directly applied to feed-forward networks and feed-forward (recurrent) networks. There are quite many types of ANNs, such as simple perceptrons, CNN, recurrent networks, and ANNs with long short-term memory.

Literature review. The works of H. Bourlard [1], Dupont [2], A. P. Dempster [3], N. M. Laird [4] studied in studied various methods of speech recognition. A. Esposito [5] and M. Marinaro [6] attempted to make efforts to model and apply nonlinear in m papers and to propose nonlinear models of its dynamics. In his scientific work, he attempted to reveal the concept of nonlinearity in speech, revising several nonlinear speech phenomena and engineering efforts to model them. P. A. Brown [7] defended his famous doctoral dissertation on the problem of acoustic modeling in Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)

Research Methodology. The article uses the methods of synergistic, analogical, analytical, synthesis, analysis, observation, experimental methods of scientific knowledge.

Analysis and results. Voice unity acoustic automatic speech recognition (ASR) is a crucial component in modeling . Current ASR systems use a hidden Markov model (HMM) to deal with temporal variability, and a Gaussian model (GMM) is used for acoustic modeling. There are many techniques for acoustic modeling of speech, and the most widely adopted by researchers is the Artificial Neural Network (ANN).

An alternative approach to acoustic modeling is the use of neural networks (NNs). Neural networks are capable of solving complex recognition problems, but they do not scale to the same extent as HMMs when dealing with large word sets. For this reason, such systems are rarely used in applications typically used for speech recognition, but they can successfully process and independently deliver low-quality or noisy audio signals. If reading is limited in sequence or vocabulary, it provides more accurate information than other systems.

$$y_k(t) = f(u_k(t)),$$

where $y_k(t)$ is called the activation function of the neuron. A continuous non-linear function, for example a sigmoid function, is usually chosen as the activation function.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-ax}}$$

α – is a user-selectable parameter that affects the shape of the activation function. To the most common neural network model multi-layered perceptron (KP) can be cited. of KP structural scheme in Fig . 1.2 given.

1.1 - picture . Three layered perceptron

From the network exit
 outgoing layer
 Hidden layer
 Incoming layer
 To the network access

Two major problems with automatic speech recognition (ASR) systems are acoustic and temporal modeling of speech. Speech is dynamic in nature, its spectral and changes depend on the nature of speech production of speech signals.

Figure 1.2 - probability parameters of the Hidden Markov model. **x** - current state, **y** - possible observations, **a** - transition process, **b** - exit probabilities

A speech signal is produced by moving the articulators to the various positions required for the target sound unit. Due to the variability of articulatory movement, sequences of exactly the same phonetic units are captured as speech signals, such as trajectories.

In this process, it becomes difficult to obtain accurate time-spectral information of speech units from the speech signal. Therefore, speech modeling should take into account both of the above issues.

The ASR system uses acoustic models to extract information from the speech signal. In this approach based on speech recognition, the basic recognition units are based on acoustically modeled lexical description. Thus, the control of temporal and spectral variability is the main task of ASR.

Known speech recognition technology prefers a hidden Markov model (HMM) to provide a solution.

Speech recognition systems typically have two components that can be divided into blocks or subroutines - acoustic and linguistic. The language part can include phonetic, phonological, morphological, syntactic and semantic models of the language. The acoustic model is responsible for representing the speech signal. The linguistic model interprets the data from the acoustic model and is responsible for presenting the resulting output to the user. Modern universal speech recognition systems are usually based on hidden Markov models (HMM). It is a statistical model that describes random sequences of characters or quantities. A Hidden Markov Model (HMM) is a statistical Markov model in which the system being modeled is called a Markov process.

An alternative approach to acoustic modeling is the use of neural networks (NNs). Neural networks are capable of solving more complex speech recognition problems, but they don't scale to the same level as HMMs when dealing with large sets

of words. Such systems are rarely used in speech recognition applications, but they can successfully process low-quality or noisy audio signals. Dynamic signal scaling (dynamic timing - DTW). Dynamic Scaling (DMS) was originally used for speech recognition, but was later replaced by more efficient HMM systems. An algorithm is used to establish similarity between two time series that may be changing at different rates.

Speech recognition is the task of a machine or program to identify words and phrases in spoken language and convert them into a computer-readable format. Rudimentary speech recognition programs have a limited vocabulary of words and phrases that they can only recognize if they are clearly expressed. Sophisticated software has the ability to

1.3- picture Disabled people of the carriage common work principle

understand natural speech.

Early scientists created a prototype of a voice-controlled wheelchair. This wheelchair is designed for physically challenged people who have mobility issues

and cannot use certain mechanical devices. For this reason, scientists have developed a different way of controlling a wheelchair, voice control.

The voice controlled wheelchair and ultrasonic sensor system is shown in figure 1.4 and described in the following process.

Speech recognition devices are widely used in the medical field, in robotics and assistive functions for the disabled, as well as in many speech recognition applications. Some smartphones make interesting use of speech recognition. Examples are iPhone and Android devices. With them, you can start calling a contact by accepting spoken instructions like Call of Office. Other commands can also be enabled, such as "Enable

Bluetooth". Speech Recognition Problems In an application called Speech to Text (STT), speech recognition has long been used to translate spoken words into text.

1.4 – picture. Voice to text android app

Conclusion. In this article, the author presents concepts and proofs of acoustic modeling of the speech signal. Acoustic model units of speech are an integral part of automatic speech recognition (ASR) systems. The main goal of acoustics is to model sound units based on information obtained from acoustic feature vectors. The nonlinear dynamic nature of the speech signal makes acoustic modeling a challenging task. In the article, the main types of acoustic modeling are observed and effective approaches are analyzed. These are statistical modeling and nonlinear modeling approaches based on ANN. HMM can handle the temporal and spectral variability of the speech signal originally input for acoustic modeling.

ANN is more suitable for acoustic modeling. In addition, the computational unit of ANN, which is inherently non-linear, makes it more suitable for speech sound unit modeling. Thus, HMM/GMM-based systems are gradually being replaced by HMM/ANN systems and are increasingly being used.

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